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1 Introduction

1.1 Identification

This document is identified as S5P+I-SO2LH-D4-ATBD-v4.

1.2 Purpose and objective

The present document is the Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD) describing the theoretical basis and the implementation of the S5p+I SO₂ LH product from Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI measurements.

The purpose of the document is to give detailed mathematical description of the algorithm and to discuss the necessary input and auxiliary data, and the output that will be generated. In addition, information about the expected size of the product, expected calculation times, and the expected accuracy are provided.

The document is maintained during the development phase of the data products in the context of the ESA S5p+I project. This is the final version of the document.

1.3 Document overview

Section 1, 2 and 3 provide the introduction, references and lists of acronyms, as well as terms and definitions used in this document. Section 4 describes the context of the algorithm, a general overview, heritage from other missions or projects, and the output product. Section 5 specifies the algorithm including a high level block diagram and details about each main component. Section 6 discusses the feasibility of the algorithm as a L2 processor. Section 7 provides an error analysis. Section 8 gives a description how the algorithm can be validated.

2 Applicable and reference documents

2.1 Applicable documents

There are no applicable documents

2.2 Standard documents

[SD1] Space Engineering – Software.
source: ESA/ECSS; **ref:** ECSS-E-ST-40C; **date:** 2009-03-06.

2.3 Reference documents

- [RD1] S5P+I: SO₂ LH Auxiliary data User Manual v2.
source: DLR, AUTH; **ref:** S5P+I-SO2LH-D3-AUM2; **issue:** 2.0; **date:** 2021-07-15.
- [RD2] S5P+I: SO₂ LH Requirements Baseline Document.
source: DLR, AUTH; **ref:** S5P+I-SO2LH-D1-RB; **issue:** 1.0; **date:** 2020-01-10.
- [RD3] TROPOMI Instrument and Performance Overview.
source: KNMI; **ref:** S5p-KNMI-L2-0010-RP; **issue:** 0.10.0; **date:** 2014-03-15.
- [RD4] Sentinel-5 Level-2 Prototype Processor Development Requirements Specification.
source: ESA; **ref:** S5-RS-ESA-GR-0131; **issue:** 1.7.
- [RD5] Sentinel-5 Precursor Ground Segment PDGS Statement of Work.
source: ESA; **ref:** S5P-RS-ESA-SY-0031; **issue:** 2.0.
- [RD6] Sentinel-5 Precursor/TROPOMI SO₂ Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document.
source: BIRA; **ref:** S5P-BIRA-L2-400E-ATBD; **issue:** 2.1.0; **date:** 2020-02-28.
- [RD7] Sentinel-5 Precursor/TROPOMI O₃ Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document.
source: DLR; **ref:** S5P-L2-DLR-ATBD-400A; **issue:** 2.1.0; **date:** 2020-02-28.
- [RD8] Sentinel-5 Precursor/TROPOMI Level 2 Product User Manual O₃ Total Column.
source: DLR; **ref:** S5P-DLR-L2-PUM-400A; **issue:** 2.1.0; **date:** 2020-02-28.
- [RD9] Sentinel-5 Precursor/TROPOMI ATBD Cloud Products.
source: DLR; **ref:** S5P-DLR-L2-ATBD-400I; **issue:** 2.1.0; **date:** 2020-02-28.
- [RD10] Sentinel-5 Precursor/TROPOMI Level 2 Product User Manual Cloud Properties.
source: DLR; **ref:** S5P-DLR-L2-PUM-400I; **issue:** 2.1.0; **date:** 2020-02-28.
- [RD11] S5P+I: SO₂ Layer Height Validation Report v2.
source: DLR, AUTH; **ref:** S5P+I-SO2LH-D5-VR-v2; **issue:** 2.0; **date:** 2021-07-16.

2.4 Electronic references

- [ER1] URL <https://atmos.eoc.dlr.de/so2-lh/datapool/>.
- [ER2] URL <http://www.tropomi.eu/data-products/isrf-dataset/>.

3 Acronyms, terms and Definitions

3.1 Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

AAI	Aerosol absorption index
ALH	Aerosol layer height
AOD	Aerosol optical depth
AK	Averaging kernel
AIRS	Atmospheric InfraRed Sounder
AMF	Airmass factor
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
BRDF	Bidirectional reflectance distribution function
DOAS	Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy
EISF	Extended Iterative Spectral Fitting
FP_ILM	Full Physics Inverse Learning Machine
IASI	Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer
ISRF	Instrument Spectral Response Function
LIDORT	Linearized Discrete Ordinate Radiative Transfer
LH	Layer Height
LUT	Look-up table
MLPR	MultiLayer Perceptron Regression
MLS	Microwave Limb Sounder
MSE	Mean squared error
NN	Neural Network
NRT	Near real time
PBL	Planetary Boundary Layer
PC	Principal component
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PCR	Principal Component Regression
O ₃	Ozone
OE	Optimal Estimation
OMI	Ozone Monitoring Instrument
RAA	Relative azimuth angle
RRS	Rotational Raman Scattering
RTM	Radiative transfer model
S5P	Sentinel-5 Precursor
S5 L2PP	Sentinel-5 Level 2 Prototype Processor
SAA	Solar azimuth angle
SCD	Slant column density
SO ₂	Sulfur dioxide
SZA	Solar zenith angle
TROPOMI	Tropospheric Ozone Measurement Instrument
VAA	Viewing azimuth angle
VCD	Vertical column density
VZA	Viewing zenith angle

4 Introduction to the SO₂ LH product

Volcanic eruptions eject large amounts of ash (aerosols) and trace gases such as sulfur dioxide (SO₂) into the atmosphere. The ability to quantify the spatial extent and actual magnitude of these ejecta was shown to have a considerable impact on air traffic safety as well as on human health. Regular and comprehensive ground-based monitoring, i.e. with the ability for proper quantitative forewarning on the eruptive magnitude, is carried out at only a limited number of volcanoes. The vast amount of continuously erupting volcanoes is remotely located and hence ground-based monitoring is very limited. Hence, near-real-time (NRT) global observations of SO₂ total vertical column density (VCD), SO₂ layer height (henceforth, SO₂ LH) and aerosol load derived from satellite measurements provide unique and important information to quantitatively assess the possible impact of volcanic eruptions on air traffic control and public safety. The need for operational as well as accurate (≤ 2 km in altitude) SO₂ LH information became quite pronounced shortly after the Eyjafjallajökull (2010) and Grimsvötn (2011) eruptions.

Based on UV earthshine measurements, SO₂ VCD can be retrieved easily using for example the Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy (DOAS) technique (see e.g. [Rix et al., 2012]), or a Principal Component Analysis (PCA, see e.g. [Li et al., 2017]). These methods are fast enough for near-real-time (NRT) retrievals. Nevertheless, current operational DOAS and PCA algorithms retrieve only the slant column density (SCD). In order to calculate the VCD, explicit or implicit assumptions about the vertical distribution of SO₂ have to be made to determine the effective light path - this VCD conversion factor is called the Air Mass Factor (AMF). In the UV range between 305 - 335nm, AMFs are calculated by means of multiple-scattering radiative transfer models (RTM) using known or assumed vertical distributions of SO₂. In these models also the spectral contribution of O₃ has to be considered since it interferes with SO₂ absorption lines.

The SO₂ VCD is strongly dependent on the vertical distribution of SO₂ (in terms of the plume layer height), a quantity which is usually unknown at the time of the measurement. Even if there are ground-based or aircraft measurements of the SO₂ LH, the data are generally difficult to use for validation, since e.g. for strong eruptions, volcanic plumes are typically transported over long distances and the number of collocations is small. Thus, for volcanic SO₂ measurements, the vertical distribution of SO₂ is a key parameter limiting the product accuracy.

The direct determination of the vertical distribution of SO₂ based on satellite data is, unsurprisingly, challenging, since the information about the vertical distribution is not easily extracted from the spectral signature (see [Yang et al., 2009] and [Nowlan et al., 2011]). The SO₂ loading (or VCD) has a direct effect on the optical depth, whereas the layer height has an indirect effect on the optical depth since it influences both the number of photons passing through the SO₂ layer as well as the layer optical depth due to the temperature dependency of the SO₂ absorption cross-sections [Yang et al., 2009]. The altitude of an SO₂ layer determines the proportion of backscattered photons that pass through this absorbing layer towards the sensor. Clearly, more photons are Rayleigh-backscattered in the overlying atmosphere when the layer is lower in the atmosphere, resulting in fewer photons transmitted through the layer, and vice versa.

The TROPOMI (Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument) is the payload instrument for the Sentinel 5 Precursor (S5P) Mission. The S5P platform was launched into a sun-synchronous low-earth orbit in 2017. TROPOMI is a nadir-viewing atmospheric chemistry instrument measuring at moderate spectral resolution from the UV to the near infrared. The spatial resolution was initially 7.2 x 3.6 km² and has been increased to 5.6 x 3.6 km² on the 6th of August 2019. A description of the TROPOMI instrument and performance can be found in [RD3].

4.1 Heritage

To date, direct SO₂ plume height retrievals using satellite UV backscatter measurements from e.g. the OMI (Ozone Monitoring Instrument) or GOME-2 (Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment-2) are very time-consuming, since the spectral information content and its characterization require computationally demanding radiative transfer modelling: [Yang et al., 2009] developed an Extended Iterative Spectral Fitting (EISF) algorithm for the Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) aboard the NASA Aura satellite, which iteratively solves the linear fit equation by minimizing differences between measurements and forward model computations. [Nowlan et al., 2011] uses an optimal estimation (OE, [Rodgers, 2000]) scheme for the retrieval of the SO₂ VCD and LH based on Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment-2 instrument (GOME-2) data. Details can be found in [RD2].

Recently, new algorithms have been developed that are much faster than direct fitting approaches. The Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB) have developed an SO₂ LH algorithm in the framework of the Sentinel-5 L2PP SO₂ product development which is conceptually quite close to the EISF algorithm using a look-up-table (LUT) approach to replace the radiative transfer calculations. It is based on a modified DOAS algorithm where SO₂ optical depth (OD) spectra are used in the DOAS fit.

[Hedelt et al., 2019] have developed an algorithm called 'Full-Physics Inverse Learning Machine' (hereafter referred to as FP_ILM) for the retrieval of the SO₂ LH based on Sentinel-5 precursor/TROPOMI data using a coupled Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Neural Network (NN) approach including regression. This algorithm is an improvement of the original FP_ILM algorithm developed by [Efremenko et al., 2017] for the retrieval of the SO₂ LH based on GOME-2 data using a Principal Component Regression (PCR) technique. Recently, [Fedkin et al., 2020] have applied FP_ILM algorithm to retrieve the SO₂ LH based on OMI data. The FP_ILM algorithm has also been used for the retrieval of ozone profile shapes [Xu et al., 2017] and the retrieval of surface properties accounting for bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) effects [Loyola et al., 2020].

In general, the FP_ILM algorithm creates a mapping between the spectral radiance and atmospheric parameter using machine learning methods. The time-consuming training phase of the algorithm using radiative transfer model calculations is performed off-line, and only the inversion operator has to be applied to satellite measurements - this makes the algorithm extremely fast and it can thus be used in near-real time processing environments.

More details about other SO₂ LH retrieval approaches (either direct or indirect and applied to other satellite datasets) can be found in [RD2].

4.2 Requirements

An overview about scientific and operational requirements can be found in [RD2] and are summarized in Table 1. To summarize, independent information on the SO₂ height can be obtained typically when the SO₂ signal is strong enough, i.e. greater than about 10-30 DU (see e.g. [Nowlan et al., 2011]).

The scientific requirements formulated for the development of an SO₂ product for the upcoming Sentinel-5 satellite (see [RD4]) are followed, which specify an uncertainty of the SO₂ LH to be smaller than 1 km (breakthrough) to 2 km (threshold) for SO₂ VCD \geq 25 DU (Requirement S5-L2-PRO-220 in [RD4]). For the operational requirements, the Sentinel-5p processing requirements has to be followed (see requirement PDGS-REL-100 in [RD5]), specifying that L2 products have to be retrieved within 3 h after sensing. Since the main S5P/TROPOMI L2 products already occupy most of the processing time, an SO₂ LH retrieval should take significantly less time than the SO₂ VCD retrieval.

Requirement	Value	Source
SO ₂ LH (threshold)	< 2 km for SO ₂ VCD \geq 25 DU	S5-L2-PRO-220 in [RD4]
SO ₂ LH (breakthrough)	< 1 km for SO ₂ VCD \geq 25 DU	S5-L2-PRO-220 in [RD4]
Timeliness	3 h after sensing	PDGS-REL-100 [RD5]

Table 1: SO₂ LH retrieval requirements.

5 Algorithm description

Conceptually, the FP_ILM SO₂ LH algorithm consists of a training phase, in which the inversion operator is obtained using synthetic data generated with an appropriate radiative transfer model, and an operational phase, in which the inversion operator is applied to S5P/TROPOMI measurements. The main advantage of the FP_ILM over classical direct fitting approaches is that the time-consuming training phase involving complex RT modeling is performed offline; the inverse operator itself is robust and computationally simple and therefore extremely fast. The algorithm relies on the algorithm described in [Hedelt et al., 2019] with some differences in the algorithm settings.

The FP_ILM SO₂ LH algorithm makes direct use of the TROPOMI L2 SO₂ product. It is triggered for pixels exceeding a certain SO₂ threshold (as defined in the following) and for pixels which are flagged in the operational product as having an enhanced SO₂ amount. This L2 flag is based on a threshold criterion which also takes into account the neighboring pixels to discriminate between noise and an actual SO₂ plume, see [RD6] for details. Furthermore it uses several parameters stored in the L2 product to perform the retrieval. The output parameters of the algorithm are the SO₂ LH, an optimized SO₂ VCD and AMF as well as error estimates.

Parameter	Source
O ₃ cross-section	[Serdyuchenko et al., 2014]
SO ₂ cross-section	[Bogumil et al., 2003]
Temperature/Pressure profile	US standard profile based on [Lamsal et al., 2004], with finer gridding in lower atmosphere
O ₃ profile	TOMS v7 [McPeters et al., 1998]
SO ₂ profile	Gaussian SO ₂ profile with 2.5 km FWHM at varying LH z_{SO_2}

Table 2: LIDORT-RRS input parameters for generating reflectance spectra.

5.1 Training phase

5.1.1 Generation of training dataset

During the training phase, the Linearized Discrete Ordinate Radiative Transfer model (LIDORT) with inelastic rotational Raman scattering (RRS) implementation [Spurr et al., 2008] is deployed to compute a simulated high-resolution (i.e. $\Delta\lambda = 0.05$ nm) reflectance spectra LUT in the wavelength range 311 – 335 nm. These spectra depend upon the following $n = 8$ input parameters: the SO₂ VCD and LH, the surface albedo, the surface height, the O₃ VCD, the solar zenith angle (SZA), the viewing zenith angle (VZA) and the relative azimuth angle (RAA). From the SZA, VZA, and RAA the scattering angle is calculated, which is used instead of the RAA furthermore in the FP_ILM training and application, since it enables a smoother transition across the satellite orbit. Note that O₃ VCD has to be included due to the strong spectral interference between SO₂ and O₃ in the spectral range considered.

O₃ profiles are classified according to the total column amount of ozone as specified in the TOMS Version 7 O₃ profile climatology [McPeters et al., 1998]. The SO₂ plume profile is taken to have a Gaussian profile, characterized by the total SO₂ VCD loading and centered at a layer height z_{SO_2} , along with a width fixed to 2.5 km FWHM. In the following, the retrieval of SO₂ LH refers to the retrieval of the SO₂ layer mid-height z_{SO_2} .

Simulations were performed on a pressure/temperature/height grid from the US standard atmosphere. Note that the original vertical grid resolution has been increased to a resolution of 0.25 km below 15 km altitude in order to properly resolve the SO₂ plume shape. Temperature-dependent absorption cross-sections of O₃ from [Serdyuchenko et al., 2014] and SO₂ from [Bogumil et al., 2003] were used. In total, 541,345 simulated reflectance spectra have been calculated on a selective parameter grid established by means of a smart sampling technique developed by [Loyola et al., 2016]. Table 3 lists all input parameter for the LIDORT-RRS model, see also [RD1]. After an extended sensitivity study, Table 2 shows a summary of the final optimized parameter space for which in total 541,345 reflectance spectra have been simulated, which will be used for training and validating the algorithm. Note that in principle a broader parameter range can be used, however the error in the NN retrieval increases.

The simulated high-resolution reflectance spectra are convolved with the TROPOMI Instrument Spectral Response Function (ISRF) v3.0.0 (released 2018-04-01) [ER2]. Note that the TROPOMI instrument comprises of 450 rows, which are in principle single detectors with their own ISRFs. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is about 1000 in the SO₂ wavelength range. Thus, to account for instrumental noise in the training phase, uncorrelated Gaussian noise with a fixed SNR of 1000 is added to the simulated spectral data.

The spectral dataset is randomly split into a training dataset (consisting of 90% of the entire dataset, i.e. 487,210 spectra) and a test dataset (consisting of 10% of the entire dataset, i.e. 54,135 spectra). The training dataset is used to train the PCA and NN operators and the test dataset is used to test the performance of the trained operators on untrained data.

The training spectra LUT forms the input of machine learning training phase, which is outlined hereafter. A flow diagram of the FP_ILM training algorithm is shown in Fig. 1.

5.1.2 Principal Component Analysis

To extract the information about the layer height and to reduce the dimensionality of the spectral dataset, a PCA is applied to the simulated training spectra. By thus characterizing the set of simulated measurements with fewer parameters, a simpler, more stable and computationally efficient inversion scheme can be realized.

The PCA is performed using the following steps:

Parameter	Range
SZA θ_0	0 – 75°
VZA θ	0 – 60°
RAA ϕ	0 – 180°
Surface albedo A_s	0.0 – 0.5
Surface pressure p_s	1021 – 372 mbar
O ₃ VCD N_{V,O_3}	225 – 525 DU
SO ₂ VCD N_{V,SO_2}	20 – 1000 DU
SO ₂ LH z_{SO_2}	0.5 – 25 km
Scattering angle*	45 – 180°

Table 3: Physical parameters varied for the generation of reflectance spectra.

*The scattering angle is directly calculated from the RAA, SZA and VZA and is used in the FP_ILM training and application.

Figure 1: Flow diagram of the training of the FP_ILM SO₂ LH inversion operator.

1. Scaling of the spectral dataset with $d = 161$ wavelength grid points. PC scores are highly sensitive to data scaling, and scaling of features prior to PCA assigns equal importance to all features. All reflectance spectra were scaled to the range $[-0.9, 0.9]$ using the minimum and maximum reflectance of all training reflectance spectra.
2. Construction of the covariance matrix, which stores the pairwise covariances between the different features.
3. Decomposition of the covariance matrix into its eigenvectors and eigenvalues. The eigenvectors of the covariance matrix represent the principal components (PCs, i.e. the directions of maximum variance), whereas the corresponding eigenvalues define their magnitude.
4. Sort the eigenvalues by decreasing order to rank the corresponding eigenvectors.
5. Select N_{PC} eigenvectors which correspond to the N_{PC} largest eigenvalues, where N_{PC} is the dimensionality of the new feature subspace ($N_{PC} \leq d$)

6. Construct a projection matrix \mathbf{W}_{PCA} from the leading N_{PC} eigenvectors, which can be used to transform a dataset X onto the PCA subspace X' , i.e. reducing the dimensionality, with $X' = X\mathbf{W}_{\text{PCA}}$.
7. Transform the d -dimensional input reflectance dataset X (with $d = 161$) using the projection matrix \mathbf{W}_{PCA} to obtain the new N_{PC} -dimensional feature subspace.

Note that the SciKit-learn Python library (version 0.23.2, see [Pedregosa et al., 2011]) is used to perform the PCA.

It was found that using $N_{\text{PC}} = 10$ principal components is sufficient to retrieve information about the SO₂ LH. These 10 PCs account for 99.991% of the spectral variance. The inclusion of additional PCs did not result in any improvements to LH retrievals, since higher-order PCs are increasingly affected by noise.

5.1.3 Neural Network Training

The dimensionality-reduced reflectance spectra (now with dimension $N_{\text{PC}} = 10$ instead of $d = 161$), together with the information about the O₃ VCD, the viewing angles, the surface pressure and albedo of each training data-point, form the input to train a feed-forward artificial neural network (NN) including regression and $L2$ regularization. Note here that the SO₂ VCD is not part of the training, since it depends directly on the SO₂ layer height due to the temperature dependency of the SO₂ absorption cross-section. Note that including the SO₂ SCD from the DOAS fit as a regression parameter does not improve the retrieval results. Moreover, the SO₂ SCD is also dependent on the SO₂LH. In operational SO₂ retrievals therefore a single SO₂ cross-section at a fixed temperature is used.

A Neural Network (NN) computes a function $M(Z, W_{\text{NN}})$, where Z is the input pattern and W_{NN} represents the collection of adjustable parameters in the system, i.e. a weight matrix. A cost function (also known as loss function) $E = C(D, M(Z, W_{\text{NN}}))$ measures the discrepancy between D , the desired output for the pattern Z and the output produced by the function $M(Z, W_{\text{NN}})$. The learning problem thus consists in finding the value W_{NN} that minimizes $E(W_{\text{NN}})$. The performance of such a system is estimated by measuring the accuracy on a set of samples disjoint from the training dataset, i.e. on a test dataset.

The training of the NN is thus an iterative process, in which the cost function is minimized in each time step t by computing the partial derivatives of the cost function with respect to the model parameters at each time step in order to update the parameters W_{NN} . This is done using the 'Adam' stochastic gradient-based optimizer, minimizing the Mean Squared Error (MSE) cost function

$$E(W_{\text{NN}}) = \frac{1}{2} (D - M(Z, W_{\text{NN}}))^2 \quad (1)$$

by iteratively adjusting W_{NN} as follows:

$$W_{\text{NN}}(t) = W_{\text{NN}}(t-1) - \eta \frac{\partial E}{\partial W_{\text{NN}}}, \quad (2)$$

with η being the learning rate, which is set to $\eta = 0.001$. Note that the learning rate as well as other hyper-parameters of the NN have a strong influence on the training and the optimal parameters are found empirically. In case of the learning rate, a higher or lower learning rate might either miss local minima or end up in a local minimum and thus the global minimum might not be found.

Furthermore, a $L2$ regularization term (also known as weight decay, with $\alpha=1\text{E-}5$) is added to the cost function for maximizing the generalization ability of the network. It shrinks model parameters to prevent over-fitting. By building a complex neural network, it is quite easy to perfectly fit the training dataset. When this model is however evaluated on new data (here the satellite measurements), it performs very poorly. The regularization thus modifies the cost function by adding additional terms that penalize large weight vectors and preferring diffuse weight vectors. NN weights W_{NN} are initialized using the 'Glorot uniform' initializer (see [Glorot and Bengio, 2010]) and initial NN biases are set to zero.

Note that the MLPRegressor from the SciKit-learn Python library (version 0.23.2, see [Pedregosa et al., 2011]) is used as the NN model.

Prior to the training of the neural network, all input parameters (i.e. the PCs, as well as further input and output parameters) are scaled to the range $[-0.9, 0.9]$, which is optimized for the sigmoid hyperbolic tan activation function $f = \tanh x$ of the hidden layers of the NN. Shifting and scaling input parameters allows for

Figure 2: FP_ILM SO₂ LH Neural Network Topology

a faster convergence of the learning process. Furthermore, the sigmoid activation function gives the neural network nonlinear capabilities. Note that in general input variables to a NN should be uncorrelated, which is the case here since any linear correlations in the input reflectance spectra were removed by applying the PCA. The input layer has the dimension $[16, N_{\text{Spectra}}]$, with N_{Spectra} the number of training samples (i.e. 487,210 samples).

The NN is composed of two hidden layers comprising of 40 neurons in the first hidden layer and 10 neurons in the second layer, and with the corresponding SO₂ LH as the output layer, see Fig. 2. The NN training is performed using 90% of the training dataset (i.e. 438,489 samples), and 10% of the dataset are set aside as a validation dataset within the NN training (i.e. 48,721 samples).

5.1.4 FP_ILM inversion operator

Both the PCA projection matrix \mathbf{W}_{PCA} and the trained NN form the FP_ILM inversion operator, which is stored together with the scaling parameters of the training dataset. To take into account the row dependency of the 450 TROPOMI detector rows (with their own ISRF), in principle an FP_ILM inversion operator for each instrument row needs to be trained, i.e. in total 450 inversion operators. However, in order to avoid row-to-row jumps in the resulting SO₂ LH, an inversion operator is only trained for every 50th detector row and the retrieved LH is then interpolated to the instrument row where it was measured, hence in total 10 inversion operators are trained. Note that the training input data range is identical for each trained FP_ILM operator - only the

reflectance spectra differ slightly due to the row-dependent ISRF and for each training the samples are chosen randomly.

The final trained FP_ILM operators for each 50th detector row have converged with a validation loss of about 3.8E-04, a validation score of 0.997 and a validation MSE of around 0.12 km. The performance of each trained FP_ILM operator is nearly constant across the trained detector rows - slight differences in the training performance are related to the random error inherently existing in the neural networks.

Figure 3 shows the performance of the FP_ILM training for one detector row (i.e. row 250). In the figure, the PCA explained variance ratio as a function of number of PCs (top-left panel), each PC as a function of wavelength (top-center panel), the NN training loss and validation score (bottom-left and bottom-center panel, respectively) as well as the resulting SO₂ LH as a function of true SO₂ LH (top-right panel) and the difference between retrieved and true SO₂ LH as a function of SO₂ VCD (bottom-right panel) are shown. Clearly, no sign of over- or under-fitting are seen in the NN training history. Table 4 shows the correlation, MSE and standard deviation (StdDev) between true and retrieved LH after applying the trained FP_ILM operator to the independent test dataset. Figure 4 shows the SO₂ LH as a function of SO₂ VCD for selected heights (colour coded). It is clearly visible that with increasing SO₂ VCD the difference between retrieved and true LH decreases. Already above SO₂ VCD > 20 DU the difference between retrieved and true SO₂ LH is below 2 km. The retrieval performs equally well for all heights. Figure 5 shows the dependency of the SO₂ LH results from the entire test dataset for each input parameter. Clearly, the strongest dependency is observed with respect to the SO₂ VCD (left panel in the second row of the figure). The LH also shows a slight dependency on the viewing angles. The histogram of the LH difference (lower right panel) indicates that no bias exists between true and retrieved LH. Also the spread is very low, having a standard deviation of about 0.34 km.

Parameter	Value
R ² regression score	0.998
Pearson correlation coefficient	0.999
MSE	0.11 km
StdDev	0.34 km

Table 4: FP_ILM performance overview based on closed-loop retrievals

Figure 3: FP_ILM training overview:

Top-left: PCA explained variance ratio as a function of number of PCs added in the PCA.

Top-center: Each PC as a function of wavelength with an offset of 0.1.

Bottom-left and -center: NN training loss and validation score as a function of training epoch, respectively.

Top-right: Retrieved SO₂ LH as a function of true SO₂ LH based on test dataset.

Bottom-right: SO₂ LH difference between retrieved and true SO₂ LH as a function of SO₂ VCD.

Figure 4: SO₂ LH results of closed-loop retrievals using the independent test dataset.

Top panel: Retrieved SO₂ LH as a function of SO₂ VCD for spectra with predefined SO₂ LH. Horizontal colored bars represent the true SO₂ LH.

Bottom panel: Difference between retrieved and true SO₂ LH as a function of SO₂ VCD. Horizontal colored bars display 2 km (red) and 1 km (blue) difference thresholds.

Figure 5: Dependency of the SO₂ LH results on each input parameter. In the top-left panel also the result of a linear regression between true and retrieved LH is shown. The bottom-right panel shows the histogram distribution of the LH difference.

5.2 FP_ILM dependencies

This section summarizes the dependency of the FP_ILM operator based on different training parameters.

5.2.1 Dependency on number of training samples

The dependency of the LH retrieval based on the number of training samples is investigated by training the FP_ILM operator with 90% (nominal), 75%, 50%, and 25% of the entire training dataset and determining the MSE between retrieved and true LH. As expected, the MSE decreases with an increasing number of training samples and converges around an MSE of 0.044 km, when applied to independent test data - see Tab. 5. When applying the trained operators to measured data, with decreasing amount of training data an increase of dependencies on the viewing angles and an the LH error increases, as expected.

NSamples	90%	75%	50%	25%
MSE [km]	0.044	0.046	0.047	0.057

Table 5: FP_ILM performance as a function number of training samples. Total amount of training samples is 541,345 (100%).

5.2.2 Dependency on PCA and NN settings.

The dependency of the LH retrieval based on the PCA and NN settings was investigated by varying the nominal settings (i.e. with 10 PCs and a NN topology with 40 and 10 nodes in the hidden layers, respectively). Although the effect on the MSE in closed-loop retrievals is very low (see Tab. 6), the different settings have a strong influence on the retrieved LH, especially for low SO₂ VCDs, with partly significantly higher layer heights and related higher SO₂ LH errors. The final settings were chosen after a detailed analysis of SO₂ LH retrievals of measured volcanic eruptions.

Configuration	PCA: 10 PCs NN: [32,10] nodes	PCA: 10 PCs NN: [40,10] nodes	PCA: 12 PCs NN: [32,10] nodes	PCA: 12 PCs NN: [40,10] nodes
MSE [km]	0.048	0.044	0.047	0.043

Table 6: FP_ILM performance as a function of number of PCA and NN setup

5.2.3 Row dependency

The dependency of the retrieved SO₂ LH as a function of trained detector row was investigated by using test data for detector row 250 (i.e. input data and reflectance spectra convolved with the slit function of instrument row 250) as input to a closed-loop retrieval in which the SO₂ LH was retrieved using the 10 FP_ILM operators trained for each row. The mean difference between the maximum and minimum retrieved LH of a training sample for each of the 10 trained rows as a function of SO₂ VCD is shown in Fig. 6. From the figure a mean difference of less than 2 km for VCD of about 20 DU and further decreasing to about 0.3 km with increasing SO₂ VCD. Note that this clearly correlates with the LH error found for the LH retrieval for a single row (see former paragraph) and is thus a clear measure of the random error which will be also used to determine the LH error in the operational retrieval.

Figure 6: Mean difference of the SO₂ LH retrieved for different detector rows using a fixed test input dataset for detector row 250, see text for details.

5.3 Operational phase

In the operational phase the trained FP_ILM SO₂ operators are applied to measured S5P/TROPOMI spectral data. A flow diagram of the FP_ILM SO₂ LH retrieval algorithm is shown in Fig. 7. The retrieval can be divided into five main steps

5.3.1 Data reading and filtering

First, the operational TROPOMI L2 SO₂ data is read and pixels are filtered based on the following criteria:

- SO₂ VCD (assuming a 15 km plume height) $N_{V,SO_2} \geq 15$ DU
- Enhanced SO₂ detection flag $Flag_{Enh,SO_2} \geq 1$ (i.e. SO₂ detection)
- $SZA \leq 75$ deg
- $VZA \leq 70$ deg.

For pixels fulfilling the above criteria the solar irradiance and earth radiance spectra are read from the operational L1b products. Furthermore, pixel viewing geometries and surface properties, as well as coordinates are read from the L2 SO₂ product, see Table 7. Note that the SAA and VAA angles from the L2 product are read to calculate the RAA and the scattering angle.

If no pixel fulfills the filter criteria, the SO₂ LH retrieval is not triggered and no output is generated. Note that generating a (debug) SO₂ LH product for pixels not fulfilling the above filter criteria is not useful since either the information content related to the SO₂ LH is too low in the spectra or the noise due to high viewing angles is too high.

5.3.2 Wavelength calibration

As the second step, the selected spectra are wavelength-calibrated since irradiance and radiance spectra are given on their own wavelength grid. The calibration is performed using the wavelength calibration information already determined during the DOAS fit performed for the main SO₂ product (see [RD6]):

Figure 7: Flow diagram of the FP_ILM SO₂ LH retrieval in the operational phase, i.e. application to S5P/TROPOMI measurements.

1. Solar irradiance spectra are wavelength-calibrated by $\lambda_{\text{Irrad,calib}} = \lambda_0 - P_{\text{shift}}$, using the fitted shift polynomial P_{shift} stored in the L2 SO₂ product and λ_0 the irradiance wavelength.
2. Earthshine radiance spectra are interpolated to the original (uncalibrated) irradiance grid.
3. Shift and stretch parameters from the L2 SO₂ product for each radiance spectrum are used to get the optimized earthshine reference grid to further align radiance and irradiance spectra by $\lambda_{\text{Rad,calib}} = \lambda_{\text{Irrad,calib}} - \lambda_{\text{shift}} - \lambda_{\text{squeeze}} \times (\lambda_{\text{Irrad,calib}} - 320\text{nm})$. Note that the λ_{shift} and λ_{squeeze} parameters were calculated at the center of the fit window, i.e. at 320 nm.
4. Earthshine radiance spectra are then finally interpolated to the calibrated irradiance grid $\lambda_{\text{Irrad,calib}}$, which is the final reference wavelength grid used in the SO₂ LH retrieval.

The resulting calibrated irradiance and radiance spectra are then used to calculate reflectance spectra.

5.3.3 Dimensionality reduction and NN prediction

As the third step, the PCA projection matrix \mathbf{W}_{PCA} acquired during the training phase is applied to the reflectance spectra to transform it to a lower dimension. The PCs along with the information about the O₃ VCD, SZA, VZA, scattering angle, surface albedo and surface pressure of each selected pixel forms the input parameters to predict the SO₂ LH using the trained neural network inverse function. All auxiliary parameters are extracted from the L2 SO₂ product. Note that the information about the O₃ VCD as well as cloud parameters in the L2 SO₂ are carbon-copies from the respective operational L2 products, see [RD7, RD8, RD9, RD10] as well as [Loyola et al., 2018] for details about the O₃ and cloud product.

Prior to applying the NN to the input parameters, all input parameters are scaled to the range [-0.9,0.9] using the training data scaling parameters. The SO₂ LH is retrieved using each of the 10 trained FP_ILM operators for every 50th detector row and then interpolated to the actual row where it was detected, by fitting a second-order polynomial to the LH as a function of row.

5.3.4 LH error calculation

From Sect. 5.2 it was found that the SO₂ LH of a pixel retrieved with the FP_ILM operators for different detector rows does not show a regular dependency on the row index. This dependency is fitted using a second-order polynomial and then interpolated to the measurement row. As an example, Figure 8 (left panel) shows the dependency of the LH results as a function of the 10 different FP_ILM operators applied to a selection of pixels with different SO₂ VCD (colour-coded) measured during the Raikoke volcano eruption observed by S5p on 22 June 2019. Coloured dots (connected with dashed lines) indicate the LHs retrieved using the FP_ILM operators for every 50th row, solid coloured lines show the fitted second-order polynomial and coloured crosses indicate LH interpolated to the measurement row. Clearly, a strong dependency of the LH as a function of applied FP_ILM operator can be observed, especially for low SO₂ VCD, with a difference of up to 2km.

To calculate the SO₂ LH error, the deviation from the smooth polynomial curve is treated as noise and the LH error $\sigma_{z_{\text{SO}_2,i}}$ for each pixel i is calculated from:

$$\sigma_{z_{\text{SO}_2,i}} = \frac{\max(z_{\text{SO}_2,i}(\text{Row})) - \min(z_{\text{SO}_2,i}(\text{Row}))}{2}, \quad (3)$$

with $z_{\text{SO}_2,i}(\text{Row})$ the SO₂ LH for pixel i retrieved with the FP_ILM operator trained for the instrument row Row .

The LH error as a function of SO₂ VCD for all pixels of the Raikoke S5p measurement is shown in the center panel of Fig. 8. Clearly, the error decreases with increasing SO₂ VCD and is in perfect agreement with the dependency found in the FP_ILM training (cf. Fig. 6). The final LH $z_{\text{SO}_2,i}$ and its associated error $\sigma_{z_{\text{SO}_2,i}}$ for each pixel i is shown in the right panel of the figure.

5.3.5 Improved AMF and VCD calculation

As a final step, the retrieved SO₂ LH is used to calculate an improved SO₂ AMF ($M_{\text{impr.SO}_2}$) to convert the background-corrected SO₂ SCD ($N_{\text{S,SO}_2}^{\text{back}}$) from the L2 SO₂ product to an improved SO₂ VCD ($N_{\text{V,impr.SO}_2}$):

$$N_{\text{V,impr.SO}_2} = \frac{N_{\text{S,SO}_2}}{M_{\text{impr.SO}_2}}. \quad (4)$$

Figure 8: Retrieved SO₂ LH error for the Raikoke eruption observed by S5p on 22 June 2019.

Left panel: SO₂ LH error as a function of retrieved row for selected pixels. Dots indicate the LH retrieved using the FP_ILM operator trained for different instrument rows, solid lines show the interpolated LH as a function of row and crosses mark the final interpolated LH for the measurement row.

Center panel: SO₂ LH error as a function of SO₂ VCD for all pixels.

Left panel: SO₂ LH and associated error as a function SO₂ VCD for all pixels.

Note that the altitude-dependent temperature correction of the VCD due to the temperature dependency of the SO₂ absorption cross-section is part of the AMF calculation.

The AMF calculation from the operational SO₂ product is adopted here (see [RD6]), which reads an AMF LUT generated with LIDORT version 3.3 [Spurr et al., 2008]. The LUT contains box air mass factors dependent on atmospheric pressure and altitude, viewing angle, surface pressure and albedo at three wavelengths (313, 326 and 375 nm), corresponding to three fit windows of the operational L2 product. Note that Table 5-3 of [RD6] lists details about the physical parameters defining the AMF LUT.

5.3.6 QA value calculation

In order to describe the quality of the retrieved SO₂ LH a quality assurance value (*qa_value*) is assigned to each pixel. The quality assurance value is a numerical value with a range of [0 1], with the convention that a value <0.5 means that the SO₂ LH results for this pixel should be discarded. The *qa_value* is calculated as follows:

- Initially, $qa_value(i)=1$ for each pixel (*i*) for which the SO₂ LH retrieval is triggered.
- If one of the L2 input parameters (see Tab. 7) exceeds the training data range (see Tab. 3) the $qa_value(i)$ is decreased by 25%.
- If the improved SO₂ VCD $N_{V,impr.SO_2}(i) < 20$ DU, the $qa_value(i)$ is decreased by 25%.
- If the retrieved SO₂ LH $z_{SO_2}(i) < 0$ km or the improved SO₂ VCD $N_{V,impr.SO_2}(i) < 15$ DU (i.e. the initial threshold criterion triggering the SO₂ LH retrieval), the $qa_value(i)$ is set to 0. The corresponding output parameters (see Tab. 8) are set to *NaN*.

5.3.7 Pixel flagging

In addition to the QA value also a pixel-wise LH flag (*lh_flag*) is set which is calculated as follows:

- Initially, $lh_flag = 0$ for each pixel (*i*) for which the SO₂ LH retrieval is triggered (i.e. no errors or warning occurred during the retrieval)
- If one of the L2 input parameters of a given pixel *i* exceeds the trained data range, the flag is increased by 1 (i.e. input limit warning).

- If the output SO₂ LH $z_{\text{SO}_2}(i)$ of a given pixel i exceeds the trained output data range, the flag is increased by 2 (i.e. output limit warning).
- If the aerosol absorption index $\text{AAI}(i) \geq 2$, the flag is increased by 4 (i.e. absorbing ash present warning).
- If the aerosol absorption index $\text{AAI}(i) < 0$, the flag is increased by 8 (i.e. non-absorbing sulfate aerosol present warning).
- If the improved SO₂ VCD $N_{\text{V,impr.SO}_2}(i) \leq 15 \text{ DU}$ for a given pixel, the flag is increased by 16 (i.e. improved VCD below limit error).
- If the SO₂ LH $z_{\text{SO}_2}(i) < 0 \text{ km}$, the flag is increased by 32 (LH below zero error).

With this flag, the user can easily set-up his own filter. For example, a very conservative user might only use pixels with $lh_flag == 0$ and $qa_value == 1.0$, whereas the common user already gets good results with $lh_flag < 16$ and $qa_value \geq 0.5$.

5.3.8 Input

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Range	Source
Earth radiance	I	[mol s-1 m-2 nm-1 sr-1]		S5p L1b (BD3)
Solar irradiance	I_0	[mol s-1 m-2 nm-1]		S5p L1b (IRR)
SZA	θ_0	[degree]	[0 – 75]	S5P L2 SO ₂
VZA	θ	[degree]	[0 – 70]	S5P L2 SO ₂
SAA*	ϕ_0	[degree]	[0 – 360]	S5P L2 SO ₂
VAA*	ϕ	[degree]	[0 – 360]	S5P L2 SO ₂
Latitude center and corner coordinates		[degree]	[-90 – 90]	S5P L2 SO ₂
Longitude center and corner coordinates		[degree]	[-180 – 180]	S5P L2 SO ₂
SO ₂ SCD	N_{S,SO_2}	[mol m-2]		S5P L2 SO ₂
SO ₂ SCD error	$\sigma_{N_{S,SO_2}}$	[mol m-2]		S5P L2 SO ₂
SO ₂ background corrected SCD	N_{S,SO_2}^{back}	[mol m-2]		S5P L2 SO ₂
SO ₂ corrected SCD error	$\sigma_{N_{S,SO_2}^{back}}$	[mol m-2]		S5P L2 SO ₂
SO ₂ VCD for 15km	N_{V,SO_2}	[mol m-2]		S5P L2 SO ₂
SO ₂ fitting window flag		n.u.	[1-3]	S5P L2 SO ₂
Enhanced SO ₂ detection flag	Flag _{Enh.SO2}	n.u.		S5P L2 SO ₂
O ₃ VCD	N_{V,O_3}	[mol m-2]		S5P L2 SO ₂
Surface albedo	A_s	n.u.	[0-1]	S5P L2 SO ₂
Surface pressure	p_s	[Pa]	[1e4 – 1e5]	S5P L2 SO ₂
Cloud albedo	A_c	n.u.	[0 – 1]	S5P L2 SO ₂
Cloud pressure	p_c	[Pa]	[1e4 – 1e5]	S5P L2 SO ₂
Cloud fraction	cf	n.u.	[0 – 1]	S5P L2 SO ₂
Aerosol Absorption Index**	AAI	n.u.		S5P L2 SO ₂
Aerosol Layer Height**	ALH	[m]		S5P L2 AER_ALH
Wavelength calibration radiance squeeze	<i>squeeze</i>	[nm]		S5P L2 SO ₂
Wavelength calibration radiance shift	<i>shift</i>	[nm]		S5P L2 SO ₂
Wavelength calibration polynomial	P_{shift}	n.u.		S5P L2 SO ₂
AMF LUT				Lidort v3.3
AMF Error LUT				Lidort v3.3

Table 7: Input parameters for the operational FP_ILM SO₂ LH retrieval.

*SAA and VAA are used to calculate the RAA and scattering angle

**AAI and ALH are used to flag pixels in an ash/aerosol plume

5.3.9 Output

Parameter	Symbol	Unit
SO ₂ layer height	z_{SO_2}	[km]
SO ₂ layer height error	$\sigma_{z_{SO_2}}$	[km]
SO ₂ layer pressure	p_{SO_2}	[hPa]
SO ₂ layer pressure error	$\sigma_{p_{SO_2}}$	[hPa]
SO ₂ improved VCD	$N_{V,impr.SO_2}$	[DU]
SO ₂ improved VCD error	$\sigma_{N_{V,impr.SO_2}}$	[DU]
SO ₂ improved AMF	$M_{impr.SO_2}$	n.u.
SO ₂ improved AMF error	$\sigma_{M_{impr.SO_2}}$	n.u.
QA value	qa_value	n.u.
LH flag	lh_flag	n.u.

Table 8: Output parameters from the FP_ILM SO₂ LH retrieval.

6 Feasibility

6.1 Auxiliary Data

A summary of auxiliary data required to run the SO₂ LH retrieval can be found in [RD1].

6.1.1 Training inputs

In order to train the FP_ILM, table 2 lists the static inputs.

6.1.2 Operational inputs

For the operational SO₂ LH retrieval, table 7 lists the dynamic inputs.

6.1.3 Configuration parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Value	Description
Enhanced SO ₂ detection flag	Flag _{Enh.SO2}	n.u.	≥1	Flag value from the L2 SO ₂ product indicating presence of enhanced SO ₂
Vertical column threshold	$N_{V,SO2}$	[DU]	≥15	SO ₂ VCD from L2 SO ₂ product above which the SO ₂ LH retrieval is triggered
SZA threshold	θ_0	[degree]	≤75	SZA threshold below which the SO ₂ LH retrieval is triggered
VZA threshold	θ	[degree]	≤75	VZA threshold below which the SO ₂ LH retrieval is triggered
Improved vertical column threshold	$N_{V,impr.SO2}$	[DU]	≥15	Improved SO ₂ VCD calculated with the retrieved SO ₂ LH, above which the retrieved SO ₂ LH is deemed valid
Wavelength interval SO ₂ LH retrieval	λ	[nm]	[311 – 335]	Wavelength interval used for SO ₂ LH retrieval
Number of PCs	N_{PC}	n.u.	12	Number of PCs fitted in PCA for dimensionality reduction
Neural network hidden layer size		n.u.	[40,10]	Size of the two hidden layers of the NN
Neural network activation function	f	n.u.	$\tanh.x$	Activation function for each hidden layer in the NN
Neural network L2 regularization parameter	α	n.u.	0.0001	L2 regularization parameter for each hidden layer in the NN

Table 9: Overview of general configuration parameters

6.2 Estimated computational effort

The Sentinel-5p sensor TROPOMI samples the Earth's surface with an unprecedented spatial resolution of 7.2 x 3.6 km² at best (5.6 x 3.6 km² from 6 August 2019). Spectral measurements in Band 3 are delivered with a size of 6 GB per orbit, with 15 orbits daily and about 1,5 Mio. spectra per orbit. L2 SO₂ data has a size of about 930 Mb per orbit. The SO₂ LH algorithm only needs to read S5P L1b data, L2 SO₂ data and the inversion operator (currently stored as a Python pickle file) as well as the AMF and AMF error LUT as auxiliary input.

In order to estimate the computational effort for TROPOMI retrievals, tests have been performed on a personal computer (i.e. Intel Core i7-6700 with 32GB RAM and 1.5Tb HDD) assuming 50,000 selected pixels, i.e. about 3% of the entire orbit. Note that even in a very pessimistic scenario of an extreme eruption such as Pinatubo only about 10% of the pixels of a given orbit needs to be processed. The largest volcanic eruptions detected by satellites so far (e.g., Raikoke, Kasatochi, Sarychev, Nabro) lead to typically 1-3% of pixels to be processed for a limited number of orbits. Table 10 provides an overview about the estimated processing time of each retrieval step.

Retrieval step	Time per pixel	Total time
L2 SO ₂ reading	0.1 ms	5 s
L1b irradiance spectrum reading		0.05 s
L1b radiance spectrum reading	6 ms	300 s
Wavelength calibration	0.3 ms	15 s
PCA and NN prediction	0.2 ms	10 s
Total	6.6 ms	330 s

Table 10: Estimated computational effort for each retrieval step of the SO₂ LH retrieval. Total time is calculated assuming 50,000 selected pixels.

6.2.1 Output product overview

Table 11 gives a minimum set of data fields that will be present in the SO₂ LH L2 output product. More details about the L2 data format will be provided in an associated Product User Model (PUM).

7 Error Analysis

From closed-loop tests on independent synthetic data, a theoretical uncertainty of < 2 km for VCD > 20 DU was found. Also the random error of the FP_ILM retrieval inherently existing in the NN retrieval was found to perfectly correlate with the theoretical uncertainty, cf. Section 5.2.

From preliminary results of recent volcanic eruptions, it was also found that the SO₂ LH agrees with LH results from other sources (e.g. IASI, MLS, CALIOP) within 2 km.

Based on this error estimate, the AMF error $\sigma_{M_{\text{impr.SO}_2}}$ and VCD error $\sigma_{N_{V,\text{impr.SO}_2}}$ has to be calculated. Since the background-corrected SO₂ SCD $N_{S,\text{SO}_2}^{\text{back}}$ is independent of the retrieved SO₂ LH, only $\sigma_{M_{\text{impr.SO}_2}}$ and $\sigma_{N_{V,\text{impr.SO}_2}}$ have to be calculated with the given SO₂ LH uncertainty.

The total improved SO₂ VCD error can be calculated via error propagation, assuming uncorrelated retrieval steps:

$$\sigma_{N_{V,\text{impr.SO}_2}}^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{N_{S,\text{SO}_2}}}{M} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{N_{S,\text{SO}_2}}^{\text{back}}}{M} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{N_{S,\text{SO}_2} - N_{S,\text{SO}_2}^{\text{back}} \sigma_{M_{\text{impr.SO}_2}}}{M^2} \right)^2, \quad (5)$$

where $\sigma_{N_{S,\text{SO}_2}}$ is the error on the retrieved SO₂ SCD N_{S,SO_2} .

The error on the improved AMF is calculated using the operational LUT of AMF sensitivities, which contains the AMF derivatives with respect to the different input parameters and which has been created using reduced grids from the AMF LUT and a parametrisation of the profile shapes based on the profile shape height, see Section 7.2 of [RD6]. Note that the uncertainty of the SO₂ profile shape is assumed to be 50 hPa (0.5 km) in the operational SO₂ product. For the improved AMF and VCD however, an uncertainty of about 200 hPa is assumed to calculate the AMF and VCD error.

Name	Symbol	Unit	Description	Data type	Dimension
Time	$time$	n.u.	Julian date of the measurement of each pixel	int	nGround x nScan
Latitudes	lat	[degree]	Latitudes of the four pixel corners + center	float	5 x nGround x nScan
Longitudes	lon	[degree]	Longitudes of the four pixel corners + center	float	5 x nGround x nScan
SZA	θ_0	[degree]	Solar zenith angle	float	nGround x nScan
VZA	θ	[degree]	Viewing zenith angle	float	nGround x nScan
RAA	ϕ_0	[degree]	Relative azimuth angle	float	nGround x nScan
Albedo	A_s	n.u.	Surface albedo	float	nGround x nScan
Cloud albedo	A_c	n.u.	Cloud top albedo	float	nGround x nScan
Surface pressure	p_s	[Pa]	Surface pressure	float	nGround x nScan
Cloud pressure	p_c	[Pa]	Cloud top pressure	float	nGround x nScan
Detection flag	$Flag_{Enh.SO_2}$	n.u.	Enhanced SO ₂ detection flag	integer	nGround x nScan
SO ₂ layer height	z_{SO_2}	[m]	SO ₂ layer (mid) height	float	nGround x nScan
SO ₂ layer top height	$z_{SO_2,top}$	[m]	SO ₂ layer top height	float	nGround x nScan
SO ₂ layer bottom height	$z_{SO_2,bottom}$	[m]	SO ₂ layer bottom height	float	nGround x nScan
SO ₂ layer height error	$\sigma_{z_{SO_2}}$	[m]	SO ₂ layer height error	float	nGround x nScan
SO ₂ layer pressure	p_{SO_2}	[Pa]	SO ₂ layer (mid) pressure	float	nGround x nScan
SO ₂ layer top error	$\sigma_{z_{SO_2,top}}$	[Pa]	SO ₂ layer top pressure	float	nGround x nScan
SO ₂ layer bottom error	$\sigma_{z_{SO_2,bottom}}$	[Pa]	SO ₂ layer bottom pressure	float	nGround x nScan
SO ₂ layer pressure error	$\sigma_{p_{SO_2}}$	[Pa]	SO ₂ layer pressure error	float	nGround x nScan
Improved VCD	$N_{V,impr.SO_2}$	[mol/cm ²]	SO ₂ VCD calculated using SO ₂ LH	float	nGround x nScan
Improved VCD error	$\sigma_{N_{V,impr.SO_2}}$	[mol/cm ²]	SO ₂ VCD error for retrieved SO ₂ LH	float	nGround x nScan
Improved AMF	$M_{impr.SO_2}$	n.u.	SO ₂ AMF calculated using SO ₂ LH	float	nGround x nScan
Improved AMF error	$\sigma_{M_{impr.SO_2}}$	n.u.	SO ₂ AMF error calculated using SO ₂ LH	float	nGround x nScan
Aerosol absorption index	AAI	n.u.	Aerosol absorption index	float	nGround x nScan
Aerosol layer height	ALH	[m]	Aerosol layer height	float	nGround x nScan
Aerosol optical depth	AOD	n.u.	Aerosol optical depth	float	nGround x nScan
QA value	qa_value	n.u.	QA value indicating quality of retrieval	float	nGround x nScan
LH flag	lh_flag	n.u.	Flag indicating warnings and errors during the retrieval	int	nGround x nScan

Table 11: List of output fields in the SO₂ LH product. $nGround$ x $nScan$ mean the number of pixels in an orbit across track and along track, respectively.

7.1 Influence of aerosols on SO₂ LH retrieval

To investigate the SO₂ LH retrieval in the presence of aerosols, an independent spectral dataset was generated using the LIDORT-RRS RT model. In addition to the parameters described in Sect. 5.1.1, also an aerosol layer was added with a variable aerosol optical depth (AOD) in the range AOD=[0–5] at an aerosol layer height (ALH) in the range ALH=[0–8] km. The optical properties of the volcanic ash from the Eyjafjallajökull volcanic eruption on Iceland in 2010 [Derimian et al., 2012] were used to simulate the Mie scattering of light on ash particles in the radiative transfer model. Note that ash properties of different volcanic eruptions may differ, having different impact on the reflectance spectra. A detailed analysis how different ash properties affect the SO₂ LH retrieval is however beyond the scope of this document. In total about 500,000 spectra were generated and new PCA and NN operators were trained with this ash dataset. Note that the same PCA and NN settings were used as in the nominal training. The following closed-loop tests were performed:

1. The nominal SO₂ LH FP_ILM operators were applied to the ash spectra dataset.

With increasing AOD and ALH, the difference between true and retrieved SO₂ LH can become as high as 10 km, see Fig. 9. When the SO₂ plume is located above the ash plume, the absolute error on the retrieved SO₂ plume height is about 5 km.

2. The SO₂ LH FP_ILM operators trained with data including ash absorption were applied to a test spectra dataset containing no ash.

The resulting SO₂ LH is overestimated by up to 5 km for SO₂ VCD < 100 DU and by up to 2 km for SO₂ VCD > 100 DU, see left plot in the second panel of Fig. 10.

3. The SO₂ LH FP_ILM operators including ash were applied to a test spectra dataset containing ash.

The error on the SO₂ LH is < 5 km if the SO₂ plume is below the ash plume, and < 2 km when the SO₂ plume is located above the ash plume, see Fig. 11.

Figure 9: Difference between retrieved and true SO₂ LH when applying the nominal FP_ILM operators to test spectra including ash absorption.

To summarize, the presence of volcanic ash has a very strong influence on the retrieved SO₂ LH. In case of the nominal trained SO₂LH FP_ILM operators, the difference between the true and retrieved SO₂ LH can be up to 10 km. When the SO₂ plume is located above the ash plume the absolute error can be up to 5 km. Training the FP_ILM operators which take ash absorption into account leads to an overestimation of the true SO₂ LH in case no ash is present and a higher SO₂ LH retrieval error of up to 5 km in the case there is indeed an ash layer present. As a result of this analysis, the operational SO₂ LH retrieval will be performed with the nominal trained FP_ILM operators (i.e. not considering ash in the training) and the user will be notified by a flag that ash might be present lh_flag, see Sect. 5.3.7. Furthermore, also the qa_value will be decreased when the aerosol index for a given satellite pixel exceeds a certain threshold.

Figure 10: Difference between retrieved and true SO₂ LH when applying FP_ILM operators including ash to test spectra without ash absorption.

Figure 11: Difference between retrieved and true SO₂ LH when applying FP_ILM operators including ash to test spectra with ash absorption.

7.2 Effect of SO₂/O₃ interference for strong volcanic eruptions

It is assumed that very high SO₂ loadings due to volcanic eruptions can produce inaccurate O₃ VCDs due to SO₂/O₃ interference. From an internal O₃ closed-loop test based on a test dataset containing SO₂ and ash for a moderate and high volcanic eruption, it was found that the operationally retrieved O₃ VCD is underestimated by up to 6 – 8% . In an ash-free scenario with high amounts of SO₂, the retrieval error of the O₃ VCD is mostly within 2% (pers. comm., D. Loyola and J. Xu). The effect of an inaccurate O₃ VCD in the presence of high SO₂ amounts on the SO₂ LH retrieval result is therefore assumed to be very low.

Figure 12: Volcanic plume of the Raikoke eruption observed by S5p on 22 June 2019. Clearly, the retrieved O₃ VCD (upper right panel) is underestimated by about 8–10% in the center of the plume. The SO₂ LH result corrected for this underestimation is shown in the lower right panel.

Two strong volcanic eruptions were analyzed furthermore, clearly showing an underestimation of the O₃ VCD inside the volcanic plume:

- During the Raikoke volcanic eruption in June 2019, clearly the O₃VCD is underestimated by about 8–10% in the center of the volcanic plume, see Fig. 12. Correcting the O₃ VCD for this underestimation only decreases the SO₂ LH by about 500 m. Note here that the underestimated O₃ VCD is related to the presence of an ash plume, which has a much stronger effect on the retrieved O₃ VCD (and SO₂ LH) than high values of SO₂ itself.
- During the Sinabung volcanic eruption on 19 February 2018 the O₃VCD was underestimated by about 5% in the center of the volcanic plume (not shown). During this volcanic eruption also an ash plume was observed. Correcting the O₃VCD results in slightly higher SO₂ LH of about 500 m

To summarize, the SO₂ interference effect on the operational O₃ VCD retrieval in the presence of strong volcanic SO₂ clouds has a negligible impact on the SO₂ LH retrieval. Thus, no operational correction of the O₃ VCD will be performed. Note however that in the presence of volcanic ash clouds the O₃ VCD can be underestimated by up to 10%. The effect on the SO₂ LH however is still very low, being in the order of about 500 m. The effect of ash or aerosols however is much higher (see Sect. 7.1).

8 Validation

In this section an initial and brief overview on the validation strategy of the SO₂ LH product is shown. For the detailed validation report, the reader is referred to the SO₂ LH validation report [RD11].

In general, the validation of the SO₂ LH product is very challenging and so far, SO₂ LH products based on satellite data were verified indirectly i.e. via the validation of the associated SO₂ VCD, for which an SO₂ LH is needed as an input for the AMF calculation. Hence comparing the SO₂ VCDs provided for the different SO₂ LHs was the only manner in which the actual plume altitude retrieved from different space-borne instrumentation could be compared. Simultaneously, in order to compensate for the differences in overpass times, spatial resolution, pixel direction, etc., typically the SO₂ mass is calculated and that quantity is used as an intermediary for the LH comparison. In this way, two IASI/MetOp-A and /MetOp-B SO₂ LH retrieval algorithms have been validated, allowing to perform a direct LH-to-LH validation assessment.

The following datasets for selected volcanic eruptions will be used for validation:

- IASI/MetOp-A and /MetOp-B, MLS, as well as sporadic CALIOP/CALIPSO observations will be used for the direct LH-to-LH validation assessments
- OMI/Aura, as well as the GOME2/MetOp-A and /MetOp-B official volcanic SO₂ datasets, which are both well-respected and extensively validated will be used for the indirect validation of the TROPOMI SO₂ LH product.
- Furthermore ash properties retrieved from IASI/MetOp-A and /MetOp-B will be used to study the impact of volcanic ash and aerosols on the SO₂ LH retrieval.
- Nota Bene: different satellite sensors have different overpass times, swaths, spatial resolutions and measurement sensitivities to SO₂ columns.

Validation activities will focus on volcanic eruptions with an extended plume such that independent satellite data with a different overpass time are also available. Although this is not a problem for IASI data (global daily coverage, low SO₂ threshold), collocated MLS and CALIPSO measurements (if available) have to be identified. Furthermore, to assess the error of the retrieved SO₂ LH in the presence of absorbing and non-absorbing aerosols, selected volcanic eruptions with known ash or sulfate emissions will also be analyzed.

Several difficulties rise in the intercomparison with ground-based observational sources of volcanic eruptive SO₂ plumes:

- The SO₂ LH retrieval is limited to high SO₂ VCDs (typically larger than 15 DUs).
- For sustained eruptions, information from ground-based instruments might not be applicable because of the fundamental obstacles in measuring in these conditions.
- Ground-based remote-sensing instruments operating close to SO₂ point sources are sensitive to fresh SO₂ plumes while a satellite sensor will measure aged plumes that may have been significantly depleted in SO₂. Furthermore the volcanic plume might have been subject to rise in altitude after injection in the atmosphere.
- For most volcanoes, there is no ground-based/in situ instrumentation to measure SO₂ during an eruption and even if that were the case, e.g. for strong eruptions, volcanic plumes are usually transported over long-distances. While those can be then observed by ground-based/in-situ measurements far from the source, as well as aircraft-born devices, only a handful of datasets is available and the number of coincidences is usually incredibly small.

9 Conclusion

The SO₂ Layer Height retrieval has so far appeared as experimental in the satellite retrieval community since it is extremely difficult to extract this type of information from the spectral fingerprint of UV Earthshine measurements in the wavelength range 311–335 nm. In the past, time-consuming direct fitting techniques have been applied to perform this task, which are computationally very expensive and hence not part of any operational satellite analysis chain.

A new approach has been developed involving Principal Component Analysis and Neural Network training that is much faster yet accurate, which even allows for the SO₂ LH retrieval in an operational environment. The retrieval can be performed within a few milliseconds per pixel, and tests on synthetic test datasets as well as an initial validation using real measurements of volcanic eruptions using Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI show an accuracy of less than 2 km of the retrieved LH for SO₂ VCD > 20 DU.

Up to now, the information about the SO₂ LH was an unknown in the radiative transfer algorithms and to calculate the SO₂ VCD a set of apriori plume heights were assumed which represented possible eruptive or outgassing scenarios. The actually retrieved SO₂ LH thus enables the provision of unique and important information to quantitatively assess the possible impact of volcanic eruptions on air traffic control and public safety.

9.1 References

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